

Assessing the Effects of Global Warming on Resource Conflict and Poverty in Kogi State: A Review

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the Effects of Global Warming on Resource Conflict and Poverty in Kogi State: A Poly-Crisis Review. Global warming has generated intense discourse amongst stakeholders, mostly amongst environmentalists and policymakers, in recent times. Through qualitative analysis, the study examines the connection between global warming and the recurring resource conflict with a focus on herder-farmer clashes. Also, the study attempts an analysis of global warming-induced poverty evident in temporary camps (IDPs), destruction of farmland and means of livelihood. The study employed Vulnerability and Eco-Violence Theories to understand the susceptibility of individuals or communities to resource conflict, harm from environmental hazards and disasters. The increasing loss of fertile land suitable for pasture resulting from desertification, reduced water availability and land encroachment, which increases the agelong transhumance routes within West Africa and has implications in exacerbating resource competition and strain relationship mostly between farmers and herders. Also, perennial flooding and depletion of the ozone layer in places like Kogi State and along the river banks of Rivers Niger and Benue make citizens susceptible to poverty, as evident in displacement, loss of habitat, disruption in the means of livelihood, disease infestation, etcetera. It is therefore suggested that widespread collaboration should be embarked upon by the Nigerian government with heavy industrial nations to reduce carbon and fossil emissions, which are causative agents of global warming/climate change.

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1.1. Introduction

The expansion of human activities, especially with the increasing level of industrialisation around the world, has led to visible changes in the climatic conditions in most countries around the world. The consequences of these changes are evident in the depletion of the ozone layer, global warming, melting of icebergs, drought, and desertification within the ecosystems of nations. Although there have been a number of high-powered policy directions, notably through the United Nations, to stem the tide, most developing countries bear the brunt of climate change. Nigeria is one of the worst-hit countries facing the consequences of global warming, as the country ranks as one of the ten most vulnerable countries to the impacts of climate change and natural hazards (World Bank Group, 2021). This is premised on the fact that Nigeria faces the challenge

of numerous natural hazards and is prone to floods along the River Niger and Benue, droughts and accumulation of greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄) in the atmosphere (Yakubu, Aliyu and Magaji, 2025). This trend is visible in Nigeria's states like Kogi State that face extensive risks from flooding.

The North – Central States in Nigeria are susceptible to global warming-induced conflict because of the risk associated with high exposure to aridity, generating high tensions between farmers and pastoralists concerning land rights as well as water access (World Bank Group 2021; Odih and Chilaka, 2012). In Nigeria, the fringes of the Northeast/west have continued to experience drought and desertification. This has led to intensified movement of herders through the agelong transhumance routes where local farmers occupy for means of livelihood through farming. This movement is often associated with deadly conflicts and clashes, which have presented a new dimension of insecurity in Nigeria (Ahmed-Gamgum, 2018). Also, widespread flooding is a recurrent disaster, especially in the last two decades. The most notable being the 2012, 2015 and 2022 floodings with attendant consequences. On the economic front, the 2012 flooding alone caused nearly \$17 billion in damages and losses in the 12 most affected states, including Kogi State, directly affecting seven million people, while the 2015 flooding resulted in damages of approximately \$25 million and directly affected one million people (World Bank Group, 2021).

On the socio – economic front, floods and droughts, two of the most notable consequences of global warming in Nigeria, have resulted in famine, population displacement, conflicts, and biodiversity loss (Rowlands and Eze, 2025). Within the North–Central, known for a volatile security, economic and political atmosphere, global warming has expanded the horizon of security and economic discussion, evident in farmers–herders violent conflict, leaving a death toll and wanton destruction. Rowland and Eze (2025) and McCarthy et al. (2025) affirmed that climate-induced security and economic disruptions are evident in flooding and drought, which have eroded agricultural productivity and livestock sectors. The implication is the constant movement of farming and pastoralist populations into already resource-stressed zones (McCarthy et al., 2025 and Rowland and Eze, 2025). The migratory nature of pastoralists in Kogi State has contributed to heightened tensions, particularly between farmers and pastoralist communities. Within Kogi State, the worst hit being Omala, Yagba East, Yagba West and Mopa Amuro local government areas, where the migration of herdsmen has become increasingly lethal in recent years - 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025, with significant loss of life and widespread human suffering (Abugu et al., 2021; Rowland and Eze, 2025; Yakubu, Aliyu and Magaji, 2025).

The paper utilizes qualitative design focused on the review of documents and secondary sources. Therefore, the study seeks:

- i. to establish the connection between climate change/global warming and persistent conflict between farmers and herders in Kogi State, and
- ii. to determine the implications of flooding on the economic survival and poverty trap of residents along the coastlines of the River Niger and Benue in Kogi State.

Literature Review

Although in some spheres, global warming and climate change are used interchangeably, there exist distinguishable parameters. While global warming is a subset or component of climate change, climate change covers a broader spectrum in environmental sustainability politics and studies. Global warming is the long-term heating of the Earth's surface arising mainly from human activities, which exacerbates the depletion of the ozone layer, which protects the ultraviolet rays, accumulation of greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) in the atmosphere. This phenomenon is primarily driven by human activities, including fossil fuel combustion, deforestation and industrial processes, which have intensified since the Industrial Revolution (Davarcioglu, 2017; World Bank, 2022; IPCC, 2021, Sule *et al.*, 2024). The implication is rising sea levels, melting glaciers, and extreme weather, with global warming being a primary driver of these changes. On the other hand, climate change is the long-term changes in average weather patterns, encompassing temperature, precipitation, wind, etc., caused by global warming, deforestation, aerosols, natural variations, etc. It is visible that these changes have negative effects on natural systems and human societies, contributing to extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and socioeconomic challenges such as food insecurity and health risks (Yakubu, Aliyu and Magaji, 2025).

Two theories are adopted to cater for specifics – resource conflict and poverty. Eco-violence, as developed and popularised by Homer – Dixon (1999), is applicable to examining the connection between global warming and resource conflict in Kogi State. The basic argument of Homer-Dixon is that large populations in many developing countries are highly dependent on four key environmental resources that are very fundamental to crop production: fresh water, cropland, forests and fish. However, it was postulated that scarcity or shrinking of these resources (fresh water, cropland, forest and fish) as a result of misuse, over-use or degradation under certain circumstances will trigger off conflicts hitherto referred to as resource conflict. Within the spectrum of resource competition in Kogi State, herders' migratory nature in search of green pasture and farmers' search for fertile land that is in short supply as a result of "overuse, misuse or degradation" may result in open confrontation and resource-based conflicts, as evident in Kogi State.

Homer-Dixon (1999) further espoused thus:

Decreases in the quality and quantity of renewable resources, population growth, and unequal resource access act singly or in various combinations to increase the scarcity, for certain population groups, of cropland, water, forests, and fish. This can reduce economic productivity, both for the local groups experiencing the scarcity and for the larger regional and national economies. The affected people may migrate or be expelled to new lands. Migrating groups often trigger ethnic conflicts when they move to new areas, while decreases in wealth can cause deprivation conflicts.

Within the framework of resource conflict in Nigeria, especially in the middle-belt, Ezenwa (2021) made a significant dive into the Eco – Violence Theory on how changing and adverse climatic conditions exacerbate scarcity, leading to poor living conditions for herders, which accentuates migration into farming communities already facing scarcity. The resultant effect is conflict between these divergent economic interest groups. To most Eco – Violence Theory proponents, the cumulative effects of global warming include dried seas leading to a shortage of fish and fresh water. Drought and desertification have also eaten up crop lands and forests, thereby making these environmental resources that trigger violence in short supply (Rowlands and Eze, 2025).

Vulnerability Theory analyses global warming and the rising poverty level in Kogi State. Vulnerability Theory was developed in 2008 by Martha Fineman and further expanded by other scholars such as Bryan Turner and Robert Goodin to provide a philosophical understanding of vulnerability, which they described as a universal and inherent aspect of the human condition. Hence, the basic emphasis of Martha Fineman (2008) on Vulnerability Theory shows a deviation from the traditional and formal concept of equality and therefore offers a critique of formal equality using an alternative framework. To Vulnerability theorists and proponents, “vulnerability is inherent to the human condition, and that government therefore have a responsibility to respond affirmatively to that vulnerability by ensuring that all people have equal access to the societal institutions that distribute resources” (Kohn, 2014).

Vulnerability Theory explicitly applies to global warming-induced poverty in Kogi State by explaining the inherent fragility of human existence and the systemic factors that influence individual and collective susceptibility to harm arising from global warming (Yakubu, Aliyu and Magaji, 2025). From the propositions of Vulnerability Theorists, it is obvious that people and residents of Kogi State are inherently vulnerable to the unavoidable dependence on the environmental formation and configuration, adversely affected by global warming. Furthermore, the theory emphasises economic, social and locational inequalities, politics of environmental hazard, with the impact mostly felt by the marginalised (poor) section of the population because of high-risk exposure. Therefore, Vulnerability Theory establishes an academic and practical roadmap for studying increasing poverty from the lens of global warming in Kogi State (Musa *et al.*, 2024).

The application of the Theory to Kogi State suggests a pattern of livelihood vulnerability which expands the poverty trap. For instance, the riverbank residents of Lokoja and its environs, where the economic livelihood depends on farming, agriculture, fishing and forest-based economies, confront existential threats from perennial flooding from the rising levels of River Niger and Benue and other climate-induced vulnerabilities. These disasters have often heightened the poverty level in Kogi State through displacement, disruption of income streams, food insecurity, etc.

1.2. Results and Discussion

Nexus between Global Warming and Resource Conflict in Kogi State

Kogi State, like most states in North – Central Nigeria, remains a hotspot for high-profile violent conflicts. Over the years, scholars, government committees and security experts

have examined the causative agents of these conflicts. While reports showed that communal clashes remain a concern, as evident in Bassa – Kwomu ethnic conflict (2015 – 2019), Aguleri – Kogi oil ownership conflict, Lokoja – Koton – Karfe crisis (2018), Patani and Pagana groups (Bagana community) over land disputes, Itama community conflict, Katubo and Ugwo communities' conflict, Ayeke and Enweli communities' conflict, etc. (Adejoh *et al.*, 2025; Odogun Punch Report 2018; Achoba and Abraham, 2023; Actioaid, 2018; Omede, 2020). The common denominator of these conflicts is claims to land ownership, economic/resources, traditional leadership, ethnic and religious issues, etc., which have fueled these crises. Therefore, there remains no direct link to global warming. However, Premium Times Nigeria (2018) gives a vivid description of resource-induced conflict from global warming. As noted, competition over land and water resources has intensified due to climate variability, desertification and population growth in Nigeria.

Northern states in Nigeria, especially those bordering the Sahel like Sokoto, Katsina, Jigawa, Yobe, Borno, Zamfara, Kebbi, are faced with desertification. According to Yahaya *et al* (2024), 50-75% of the land affected is prone to desertification driven by global warming, deforestation, and overgrazing. The direct implication is migration. Premium Times Nigeria (2018) noted that the impact of desertification in the far northern regions has forced Fulani herders to migrate southward in search of pasture, bringing them into direct conflict with sedentary farmers. For the past two decades, the constant movement of herders has frequently led to disputes over farmland encroachment and grazing rights. For instance, as seen in the earliest stage of these clashes in 2013, where Fulani herder attacks reportedly resulted in the deaths of 10 people and the displacement of over 4,000 residents in Kogi State (EUAA, 2021; Adejoh *et al.*, 2025). The study carried out by Adejoh *et al* (2025) linked the cause of the farmers/herder crisis in Kogi State to the ripple effect of global warming. This corroborates the ideal put forward by Okoli and Atelhe (2014), who argue that the farmer-herder conflict in Nigeria is primarily a resource-based struggle intensified by global warming, expanding agricultural activities, and dwindling grazing lands. The findings of Adejoh *et al* (2025) suggest that global warming and environmental degradation were also identified as significant conflict drivers in Kogi State.

One of the adaptive strategies to global warming is the movement of herds. Moses – Ojo, Aruya and Rilwan (2023) argued that pastoralists gain advantages to avert the undesirable consequences of global warming through migratory routes. Arising from these and other associated security challenges, pastoralists are forced to migrate in search of greener pastures, resulting in increased incidences of violent clashes with farmers over access to grazing spaces. The movement of herders, an adaptive strategy to visible global warming, has expanded the security and conflict with varying degrees of conflict incidents when local crop farmers engage in clear, open objection to the constant movement and settlement of herders in these areas based on economic space competition (Omede, 2020)

Global Warming-Induced Flooding and Implications on Poverty/Displacement in Kogi State

In Kogi State, weather unpredictability is evident, arising from global warming and poor facilities to predict and manage weather conditions (Okosun, Patrick and Banki, 2024).

In Kogi State, specifically, Lokoja, the State Capital, a mix of natural factors like heavy rainfall and the location at the bank of the Niger-Benue Confluence, plus human activities such as encroaching on floodplains, poor urban planning, building on water channels and water released from upstream dams, specifically, the Lagdo Dam in Cameroon, exacerbate flooding (Emmanuel and Aniekan, 2017). Meteorological and hydrometeorological studies show that the intensity, duration and magnitude of floods, drought, hurricanes and typhoons (hydrometeorological indices) around the world are accelerated by global warming (Ogunwumi and Ihinegbu, 2025; UNISDR, 2018). The most prominent of these hydrometeorological hazards is flooding, which presents the highest and most common hazards, especially in communities around the river banks in developing countries like Nigeria and Kogi State housing the Confluence of the River Niger and Benue. On the severity of flooding, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) affirms that global warming will increase global flood disasters with adverse effects on the socio - economic condition of the people affected (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022).

While flooding is a disaster of national concern, some states in Nigeria suffer the brunt more than others in the areas of expanding poverty bracket and displacement. Within Nigeria's geographical confines, as reported by NIWA (2022), cited in Okosun, Patrick and Banki (2024), floods affected 33 of the 36 states of the federation, including FCT, Abuja. The direct implication on the affected states is the displacement of over 1.4 million people, with over 612 people killed in 2022 alone (NIWA, 2022). On the economic front, an official release from NIWA stated that more than 200,000 homes and 110,000 hectares of farmland were completely or partially destroyed (NIWA, 2022). Data from Kogi State in recent years seems worrisome, considering the casualties and the overall number of people and households affected by flooding. The Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM), in collaboration with the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), the Kogi State Emergency Management Agency (KOSEMA), and the Nigerian Red Cross Society (NRCS), between 4 and 8 September 2024, identified 4 locations in Kogi State that were impacted by floods or received internally displaced persons (IDPs) due to the flooding.

The DTM assessments of the most affected locations painted a picture of the vulnerabilities of communities in Kogi State. In the two (2) local government areas (LGAs) of Kogi State that were assessed, DTM identified 798 individuals in 97 households affected by the floods (DTM, 2024; NEMA, 2024; NRCS, 2024). These individuals included IDPs who were displaced by the floods and residents who were impacted by the floods but remained in their communities. The affected population included 773 displaced individuals. Forty-one per cent (41%) of the affected houses were habitable but needed repair, twenty-six per cent were partially damaged, and 33 per cent were destroyed. In 75 per cent (75%) of the locations assessed, crop farming was among the primary sources of income, and these were affected through the washing away of farmlands and agricultural investments.

Social and economic conditions are primarily measured to determine the level of poverty in human settlements. These are embedded in the standard of living of individuals and human organisational formation over a period of time. From the studies conducted by NIWA (2024), Okosun, Patrick and Banki (2024), DTM (2024), it is an

observable fact that flooding now has a negative impact on our planet and human activities, especially within the Lokoja metropolis and Kogi State as a whole. Thus, climate change and global warming are held responsible for flood-related disasters (Nigerian Meteorological Agency, 2015). Flooding in Kogi State is more of a yearly ritual because of its time specific occurrence due to its geographical location at the Confluence of the River Niger and Benue. The most recent flooding in Kogi State with a massive impact was in 2022, which attracted humanitarian support from NEMA, Red Cross and many others. Out of the 21 local government areas, the 2022 flood affected five (5) local governments, which include Kogi (Koton Karfe), Lokoja, Bassa, Ajaokuta and Ibaji L.G.A.

The most affected communities and local government in the 2022 flooding in Kogi State include Kogi Local Government with 46 affected communities vis-à-vis Odama, Akpaku, Odama, Kpajkpazi, Kelbe, Edeha, Edegaki, Echinose, Onwari, Irende, etc. In Lokoja Local Government, 10 communities were affected, which include Ganaja Village, Kabawa road, Old Poly Quarters, etc.; Idah local government had 21 affected communities, which include Adamu, Ogerneguy, Shekere, Ugbefulu, Ogula, Ojebe, Odeke Ota, etc. Ajaokuta recorded 15 communities that are affected, including Geregu, Okpala, Agada, Manajo, Makoja, Gbaraga, Adagbo, etc., while Ibaji recorded 75 affected communities, which include Ojebe, Odeke, Ukponu, Ota, Odogu and Oti, etc.

Based on reports, the flood came with its attendant consequences. It was reported that up to 300,000 persons were displaced, 30 persons were reported death and the destruction of economic livelihood, where thousands of hectares of farmlands, livestock and fishery farms were washed away, especially in areas like Kogi and Ibaji local government. (NEMA 2022).

Analysis of the Effects of Global Warming-Induced Conflict and Poverty in Kogi State

Global warming - induced conflict and poverty form a poly - crisis where one particular problem leads to interconnected problems. Hence, global warming-induced conflict and poverty provide a negative feedback where environmental changes drive conflict over scarce resources and natural disasters, which in turn deepens poverty and exacerbates existing vulnerabilities. Uyamasi *et al.* (2024) and Ogbette *et al.* (2018) studies indicated that serious resource - based conflict frequently erupts between herdsman and crop farmers, leading to loss of lives and valuable properties. In recent times, Kogi state has become a hotbed of farmers - herders' conflict over resources, which has expanded the security discussion in the Nigerian state. The Global Terrorism Index (2015) indicates that Fulani militants (mostly herders) were the fourth deadliest terrorist group, using machine guns and attacking villages to assault and intimidate farmers. The herder-farmers conflicts have taken a new, dangerous dimension to the extent that the clashes have become frequent, culminating in killings, maiming, and in some cases burning of houses and invasion of communities (Ukase and Ityonzughul, 2020; Ahmed-Gamgum, 2018).

The pervasive nature of farmers - herders' conflicts has destroyed property and exacerbated social vices such as rapes. It is obvious that aside from the destruction of properties, socio-economic life is often brought to a halt. This results from chains of event which led to a situation where people could not freely go about their farming and socio-economic activities for fear of violent attacks. Most local governments in Kogi, like

Omala, Lokoja, Kogi, Ijumu, Yagba East/West, Mopa Amuro, have witnessed cases of violent conflict for survival between herders and farmers, which led to the loss of lives and destruction of property, therefore the emergence of insecurity due to continuous desire for vengeance (Uyamasi *et al.*, 2024). Uyamasi *et al.* (2024) further buttressed this when they noted that “the conflict between these two groups (farmers – herders) has led to the loss of properties worth millions of naira and the death of hundreds of thousands of lives, despite all these, there seems to be no solution in sight”.

The Kukah Centre Report (2018) gives insight into the collateral damage of the herders–farmers conflict in Kogi State. To further understand the connection between global warming and herders – farmers conflict in Kogi State, the Kukah Centre Report (2018) noted that:

One agenda of the Fulani conflict is the attempt to seize land. Because the weather and the rich water bodies in the state are favourable for pastoral farming, the Fulani, in an attempt to contest over these lands recourse to violent reaction. Others tie the conflict to the search for favourable weather conditions and greener pastures; the conflict in Kogi state is a result of climate change. This narrative all points to the fact that the herdsman-farmers conflict is becoming widespread. Furthermore, it was reported on the 12th November 2015 that no fewer than 22 persons (with scores missing), including women and children, were feared killed when suspected Fulani herdsman attacked nine communities (Agojeju, Ikpoba, Ojeh, Ajomojayi, Idochi, Ojijanawo, Ulaja and Oganigu communities) in Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi State (Kukah Centre Report, 2018).

Further data, as presented by the Kukah Centre Report (2018), showed the timeline of some of the casualties of the farmers–herders’ conflict in Kogi State. It was reported that on 10 December, 2017, the Figi East and West communities in Omala Local Government, a farmers–herders conflict resulted in the deaths of 10 persons, 150 were injured/displaced; 16th March, 2018, in Dekina and Omala, 32 persons were reported killed in a farmers–herders conflict, while 20 houses were burnt. Furthermore, on 19 March, 2018, Agbenema, Omala local government witnessed the death of 49 persons and 30 houses burnt as a result of farmers – herders’ conflict. In Western Senatorial District, on May 15, 2018, Ido – Gbede, Ijumu Local Government reported 10 deaths from farmers – herders’ conflicts (Kukah Centre Report, 2018).

The resource - based killings recorded between Fulani herdsman and farmers have affected most communities in Kogi State, displacing them from their farmlands and resulting in the loss of their major source of livelihood (Obi *et al.*, 2021). The frequency of violent conflicts between farmers and herders in Nigeria has disrupted socio-economic formation and peaceful coexistence. From various reports such as the Kukah Centre Report (2018), the Global Terrorism Index (2015), and Obi *et al.* (2018), the extra-judicial killings have led to the displacement of indigenous settlers in their thousands, who abandon their homes and farmlands for security and safety. On the social dimension, the recurrent conflict between herders and farmers in Kogi State hurts inter–group (religion, economic, ethnic) relations, especially in volatile areas in

Kogi State, such as Omala, Yagba East/West and Mopa Amuro, with visible occurrences of farmers–herders’ conflicts. Furthermore, due to attention given to the herders–farmers conflict and the attendant consequences, the herders – farmers conflicts have been viewed as another dimension of insecurity in Nigeria (Odih and Chilaka, 2012; Omede, 2021; Rowland and Eze, 2025; Yakubu, Aliyu and Magaji, 2025).

On the issue of climate – induced poverty in Kogi State through the lens of flood, Davies (2022) refers to flood as “a humanitarian tragedy” based on the degree to which people are vulnerable to its effects. This is based primarily on the impact of flood disasters on livelihood and other poverty measurement parameters of affected communities. Nche (2024) acknowledges that one part of Nigeria that has been negatively impacted by flood disasters is Kogi State. In the last 14 years, with the 2012 devastating occurrence, about 250 people have been reported killed, 850, 000 displaced with several damages worth millions of dollars (National Emergency Management Agency, 2018; Oyedele, 2022).

Pictorial Exerts of 2012 Flooding Scenes (Culled from Oyedele *et al.*, 2022)

The CJID (2022) report shows the devastating effect of flooding on the proliferation of IDP camps in Kogi State. CJID (2022) noted that the flood incidents that disrupted communities and village settlements in various parts of the country have negatively impacted Kogi State residents, especially in regions located along the banks of the rivers Niger, Benue and their tributaries. Data from the State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA) affirms that at least 1,380 schools and an estimated 5,550 children were affected by flooding in Kogi state between 2012 and 2024. There are over 434 displaced persons living in classrooms in schools, as reported by Kogi State SEMA (2022). SEMA (2022) further clarifies the situation when they noted that initially, they counted 1,500, but since the flood rescinded, the numbers have reduced to about 434.

The direct implication of this flood – induced displacement is felt in the standard of living, which is one of the indicators to measure poverty. Internally Displaced People (IDPs) camps are characterised by poor living conditions, lacking in basic amenities such as toilets, health facilities, potable water, adequate and secure rooms apartment needed for dignified living. This condition makes IDPs susceptible to life – threatening

health conditions like cholera (water-related illness), malaria (mosquito-induced illness), etc. Furthermore, these camps are susceptible to overcrowding where displaced families often share limited spaces, leading to cramped conditions, inadequate relief, and insufficient food, water, and non – food items are evident. Some of these often lead to psychological trauma, anxiety and PTSD (Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder).

Agriculture as a means of livelihood is mostly affected by floods in Kogi State. Agriculture, which is heavily impacted by floods and droughts, serves as the main source of income for 80% of the rural poor. The rapid rise of urbanisation and urban poverty also increases potential flood risk (Onamah *et al.*, 2025). To support this assumption, Buba *et al* (2021) assert that the 2012 flood was one of the most devastating, causing massive disruption causing rise in the poverty level in Kogi State. Statistics show that over 152,575 hectares of farmland were destroyed. An impact assessment carried out by the Kogi State Ministry of Agriculture (2012) reported that the total crop yield decreased by 560 metric tonnes (41.2%) in 2012 alone, compared to the previous year, with the overall economic loss in nine (9) local government areas put at N63.4billion (Kogi State Ministry of Agriculture, 2012; ICIR News, 2024). The 2013 flood was relatively mild in its impact on poverty level and agricultural loss, with a reported loss of 2,500 hectares of farmland, 47,526 heads of livestock lost and affected. The most recent 2025 flood reported in Kogi and Ibaji LGAs shows 10 hectares of farmland submerged (Onamah *et al.*, 2025).

The direct implication of flooding is that the primary livelihood of the affected population, where income-generating activities in the assessed area were crop and vegetable farming, has been severely disrupted (Nature News Africa). Also, the State Government, over the years, had to dispense huge amounts to mitigate the impact of flooding on the livelihood of affected individuals and communities in Kogi State. Onamah *et al* (2025) noted that in the year 2013, the state government spent N1.186 billion to relocate flood victims through the construction of 272 housing units, which commenced with the victims of the 2012 floods. This constitutes a further drain on the Kogi State Government's coffers, thereby reducing funds for developmental purposes in Kogi State.

Farm destroyed by flood at Iyano (Ibaji LGA), Kogi State, 2025

Source: Kogi State Ministry of Agriculture Archive

1.3. Conclusion and Recommendations

The interconnected and relational effects of global warming and climate change on resource conflict and poverty in Kogi State are evident based on statistics. The poly – crisis review re-echoes that climate-induced environmental conditions, such as changing and rising temperatures, drought, land degradation/encroachments, irregular rainfall patterns and flooding, have negative effects on insecurity evident in intensive competition over land, water and other natural resources primarily between herders and farmers. Also, these environmental conditions have exacerbated existing socio-economic vulnerabilities, deepened rural poverty through displacement and destruction of the economic lives of the affected people and communities in Kogi State. The perpetual connection and interconnectedness of environmental (climate change and global warming), economic and security crises have undermined the security of the people, reduced agricultural productivity, limited household incomes, increase in IDP camps through the displacement of communities. Hence, climate change and global warming are a conveyor of insecurity and widespread poverty in vulnerable and affected communities in Kogi State.

The following recommendations were put forward to help reduce the impact of climate change/global warming on insecurity and poverty in Kogi State:

- i. It is suggested that widespread collaboration should be embarked upon by the Nigerian government with heavy industrial nations to reduce carbon, fossil emissions, and other causative agents of global warming.
- ii. Kogi State Government should develop a holistic, multi – sectoral approach that focuses on the connection and interdependence of environmental change, resource conflict, and poverty. This will help to mitigate and resolve the challenges associated with climate change and global warming, especially on security and economic development.
- iii. Effective conflict resolution mechanisms should be developed by the Kogi State Government to integrate context-specific policy responses that address climate change migration, conflict prevention and poverty reduction. This can be made possible through collaborative engagement between the Kogi State Government, institutions of government, rural communities and collaborative partners such as non-governmental organisations.

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